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PRAVO NASLEĐIVANJA DETETA U OSMANSKOM CARSTVU - PRIMER BALKANSKIH PROVINCIJA CARSTVA

Uprkos tome što se tema dečijih prava, na prvi pogled, teško može povezati sa pitanjima pravnog sistema Osmanskog carstva, dubljom analizom može se jednostavno doći do zaključka da je činjenično stanje zapravo potpuno drugačije. Poslednje rečeno naročito je jasno uočljivo ako se sagledaju lokalne prilike u pojedinačnim provincijama. Osmansko carstvo – od skromnih početaka kao emirata u Maloj Aziji do jedne od najvećih imperija u istoriji čovečanstva prošlo je dug i interesantan put. Specifičnost razvitka Osmanske imperije ogleda se u konstruktivnom pristupu prema određenim segmentima institucija, prava i običaja država i naroda koje su tokom vekova pokorili. Iako je carstvo u usponu na Balkansko poluostrvo donelo sasvim novi pravno-administrativni sistem, zasnovan prvenstveno na šerijatskom zakonu, uređenju ranijih islamskih država, a naročito Abasidskog halifata, sultan je zadržao pravo da donosi posebne zakone – kanune. Ovi kanuni bili su prilagođeni provincijama carstva, s obzirom da su uvažavali lokalne tradicije i posebnosti, a jedan od primera ovakve prakse bio je poznati Zakon za Niš. Osmansko carstvo nikada nije uspeo da šarolike običaje svojih balkanskih provincija objedini u jedno koherentno pravno područje, već su se različite prakse primenjivale u pojedinačnim provincijama Rumelije, a te razlike bile su još drastičnije kada se uporede sa pravnim sistemom arapskih provincija carstva. Ovo je naročito vidljivo u naslednom pravu, odnosno pravu deta na nasledstvo ostavioca, gde su Osmanlije donele određene pozitivne novine, koje su u praksi često bile zanemarivane. Značajna specifičnost carstva ogledala se u njegovoj jasnoj podeli po konfesionalnoj osnovi na vernike i nevernike, gde su prvi bili punopravni građani, dok su drugi bili u podređenom položaju, a i sami podeljeni na tolerisane (zimije) i netolerisane nevernike, koji su bili progonjeni do nestanka ili promene vere. Sve prethodno navedeno naročito je imalo uticaja na razvitak naslednog prava i generalno položaj deteta. Za analizu prava deteta ključno je razmatranje položaja žene – majke, koja se na osmanskim sudovima pojavljivala i kao naslednik i često kao zastupnik maloletne dece, čije je pravo branila. Za razliku od čestog mišljenja da su muslimanske žene bile potpuno obespravljene, one su u Osmanskom carstvu imale određeni zakonski status, naročito kada su u pitanju bila bračna i nasledna prava, iz čega su proisticala nasledna prava deteta, koja su se razlikovala za žensku i mušku decu.

Ključne reči: Osmansko carstvo, šerijatsko pravo, nasledno-pravni položaj deteta, status žene u osmanskom društvu.

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THE RIGHT OF INHERITANCE OF CHILDREN IN THE OTTOMAN EMPIRE: THE EXAMPLE OF THE BALKAN PROVINCES OF THE EMPIRE

Although the topic of children's rights may seem difficult to connect with the legal system of the Ottoman Empire, a deeper analysis easily leads to the conclusion that the factual situation was completely different. This is particularly evident when considering the local conditions in individual provinces. In the course of its development from its modest beginnings as an emirate in Asia Minor to one of the largest empires in human history, the Ottoman Empire went through a long and interesting journey. The uniqueness of the Ottoman Empire's development is reflected in its constructive approach to certain segments of institutions, laws, and customs of the states and peoples conquered over the centuries. In the Balkan Peninsula, the empire on the rise introduced a completely new administrative law system, primarily based on Sharia law and the regulation of earlier Islamic states, especially the Abbasid Caliphate where the Sultan retained the right to issue special laws – kanuns. These kanuns were adapted to the empire's provinces, as they took into account local traditions and peculiarities; a prominent example of this practice was the famous Law of Niš.

The Ottoman Empire never succeeded in unifying the diverse customs of its Balkan provinces into a single coherent legal framework. Thus, the Ottoman Turks resorted to applying different practices in individual provinces of Rumelia. These differences became even more prominent when compared to the legal system of the empire's Arab provinces. This is particularly noticeable in inheritance law, i.e., the rights of children to inherit from a deceased relative, where the Ottomans introduced certain positive novelties that were often disregarded in practice. A significant specificity of the Empire was its clear division along confessional lines into believers and non-believers, where the former were full citizens while the latter had a subordinate status; the former were further subdivided into tolerated (dhimmis) and intolerated non-believers, who were either persecuted to extinction or forced to convert. These distinctions had a particularly strong influence on the development of inheritance law and the general status of children. In analyzing children's rights, it is crucial to consider the position of women (mothers), who appeared in Ottoman courts both as heirs and often as legal representatives of minor children, defending their rights. Contrary to the common belief that Muslim women were completely deprived of rights, they actually held a certain legal status in the Ottoman Empire, particularly in terms of marital and inheritance rights, from which the children's inheritance rights were derived, but which were different for male and female children.

Keywords: Ottoman Empire, Sharia Law, children's inheritance law status, women's status in the Ottoman society.